

Osmium Nitrido Complexes : Electronic Structure and their Relation to their Reactivity

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The nature of the chemical bonding in the Os=N group, the mutual influence of ligands and relation of electronic structure to the reactivity of nitrido complexes of osmium are examined by CNDO/2 molecular orbital calculations on $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$, $[\text{OsNX}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$, $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) and $[\text{OsNCl}_3(\text{PH}_3)_2]$. The computed trends for Os-N, *trans*-Os-L ($\text{L} = \text{Cl}, \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and *cis*-Os-X bond strengths in the complexes, as measured by Wiberg indices, charge distributions and orbital populations, suggest that the nitrido ligand is strongest π -donor ligand and the donor interactions of the N^{3-} ligand are greatly dependent on the nature of the ligands found in the *cis*- and *trans*-positions. The strength of the *trans*-Os-Cl bond is weaker than that of the *cis*-Os-Cl. The calculations confirm the experimental observations that the *trans*-halide atoms in the $[\text{OsNX}_5]^{2-}$ are easily replaced by water. The Os-N and Os-X Wiberg indices are in linear correlation with Os-N and Os-X vibrational stretching frequencies. Reactivities of osmium nitrido complexes are discussed on the basis of charge on nitrido ligand, energy and orbital contributions of lowest unoccupied molecular orbital. For these anionic osmium nitrido complexes, results favour substitution reactions and addition reactions over nucleophilic attack at the nitrido ligand. Triphenylphosphine and sulphide ions do not directly attack the nitride ligand in $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ but attack the nitride ligand in $[\text{OsNX}_3\text{L}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3, \text{AsPh}_3$) which are obtained by the reaction of $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ with L.

The nitride ion, N^{3-} is found with metal in high oxidation states¹⁻³. It is known that an N^{3-} ion acting as a ligand displays both σ -donor and π -donor properties. A number of nitrido complexes of osmium, particularly in Os^{VI} oxidation state, have been structurally characterised^{4,5}, but to the best of our knowledge, there is no report of theoretical calculations for osmium nitrido complexes. The bondings in osmium(vi) nitrido complexes were discussed by using the Ballhausen-Gray bonding model for vanadyl species. Wheeler *et al.*⁶ performed extended Hückel molecular orbital calculations for bridged nitrido complexes of d^0 -transition metal systems. Griffith and coworkers have extensively studied the reactions of nitrido complexes of osmium^{3,7}. Bishop *et al.*⁸ reported the synthesis of osmium thionitrosyl complexes by the reaction of osmium nitrido complexes with S_2Cl_2 . Alkylation of $[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$ have also been reported⁹. In this communication, we endeavour to study the electronic structure and reactivity of $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$, $[\text{OsNX}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ and $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ with the use of CNDO/2 molecular orbital calculations. In order to see whether with triarylphosphines, $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ gives phosphineimido complexes $[\text{Os}(\text{NPR}_3)\text{X}_3(\text{PR}_3)_2]$ directly or first gives $[\text{OsNX}_3(\text{PR}_3)_2]$ which reacts with PR_3 to afford phosphineimido complexes, we have also performed CNDO/2 molecular orbital calculations on the model system $[\text{OsNCl}_3(\text{PH}_3)_2]$.

Computational details :

Molecular orbital calculations were performed using a CNDO/2-U method¹⁰. The orbitals $6s$, $6p$ and $5d$ of osmium were included in the calculations. Wave functions

Fig. 1. Coordinate system for $[\text{OsNX}_4\text{L}]^n$; z-axis is out of plane.

for these orbitals were those given by Burns¹¹. The wave functions used for Br ($4s$ and $4p$), Cl ($3s$ and $3p$), O ($2s$ and $2p$), N ($2s$ and $2p$) and H ($1s$) were Slater type orbitals. The values for the orbital exponent, beta and electronegativities were taken from the literature¹². Atomic charges and overlap populations were obtained by a Mulliken population analysis¹³ and bond strengths were measured as Wiberg indices¹⁴. The coordinate system adopted for these osmium nitrido complexes is given in Fig. 1. Interatomic distances were taken from X-ray diffraction measurements⁴ of $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$, $[\text{OsNX}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ and $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$). The bond distances are given in Table 1. For $[\text{OsNCl}_3(\text{PH}_3)_2]$, interatomic distances and bond angle were

estimated and they are : Os-N = 1.614, *cis*-Os-Cl = 2.361, *trans*-Os-Cl = 2.605, Os-P = 2.430, P-H = 1.4 Å and H-P-H angles = 109.5°. All computations were performed using the QCPE 474 program¹⁵, implimented on an ICIM-6000 computer.

TABLE 1—BOND DISTANCE IN OSMIUM NITRIDO COMPLEXES

Complex ion	Bond distances (Å)			
	Os-N	<i>cis</i> -Os-X	<i>trans</i> -Os-L	O-H
[OsNCl ₅] ²⁻	1.614	2.361	2.605	-
[OsNCl ₄ (H ₂ O)] ⁻	1.740	2.340	2.500	0.95
[OsNBr ₄ (H ₂ O)] ⁻	1.670	2.486	2.420	0.95
[OsNCl ₄] ⁻	1.604	2.310	-	-
[OsNBr ₄] ⁻	1.583	2.457	-	-

Results and Discussion

Energy levels :

Energy levels in the [OsNCl₅]²⁻ and [OsNX₄]⁻ (X = Cl, Br) complexes : In Table 2 are given the molecular energies and salient features of the upper-valence orbitals which consist mostly of the osmium *d*-orbitals. It is noted that in all these complexes of C_{4v} symmetry, the h.o.m.o. is a molecular orbital of 2b₂ symmetry localised on the Os 5d_{xy} character with some *cis*-ligand contribution. It has ca 73% Os 5d_{xy} character and ca 25% *cis*-ligand character antibonding with respect to the *cis*-ligand. The calculations clearly indicate that the l.u.m.o. is the doubly degenerate 7e orbital for the [OsNCl₅]²⁻ and 6e for [OsNCl₄]⁻ complexes. The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital for [OsNBr₄]⁻ is an orbital of b₁ symmetry which is slightly lower in energy than the 6e molecular orbital. This 7e (6e) orbital is π* (OsN) in character and is never less than 90% a π*(OsN) orbital. The 7e (6e) orbital is ca 53% Os in character. The ordering of molecular energy levels which consist mostly of the osmium *d*-orbitals, in these cases is b₂ < e < b₁ < a₁ except for [OsNBr₄]⁻ where the ordering b₁ < e is obtained. This inversion may be explained by the greater *cis*-effect of bromide relative to chloride. Since the unoccupied orbital of lowest energy can be well-described as π* (OsN), the lowest energy transition is best described as *d-d* transition.

Energy levels in the [OsNX₄(H₂O)]⁻ (X = Cl, Br) : The results of the CNDO/2-U calculations are presented in Table 3, for the upper-valency molecular orbitals of *trans*-[OsNX₄(H₂O)]⁻. In these complexes of C_{2v} symmetry, *e* orbital splits into a₁(d_{xx}) and b₂(d_{yz}) pairs. The osmium *d*-orbitals subduce the following representations : d₂₂ and d_{2²-y²} both a₁; d_{xy}, a₂; d_{xz}, b₁; d_{yz}, b₂. The h.o.m.o. is an orbital of a₂ symmetry localised on the Os 5d_{xy} (73%) with *cis*-ligand (26%) contribution. This is *cis*-Os-Cl antibonding. The unoccupied orbital of lowest energy (a₁) is strongly localised on *trans*-H₂O ligand. The a₁ orbital has 8% Os character in both the complexes [OsNX₄(H₂O)]⁻. For [OsNCl₄(H₂O)]⁻, the ordering of energy levels which consist mostly of the osmium *d*-orbitals is a₂ < b₂ < b₁ < a₁, while for [OsNBr₄(H₂O)]⁻, the ordering is a₂ < b₁ < b₂ < a₁.

TABLE 2—MOLECULAR ORBITAL ENERGY FOR [OsNCl₅]²⁻ AND [OsNX₄]⁻ (X = Cl, Br) COMPLEX IONS

Level	Energy eV	% Contributions			
		Os	<i>cis</i> -X	N	<i>trans</i> -Cl
[OsNCl ₅] ²⁻					
8a ₁	+16.315 3	63	8	22	5
4b ₁	+14.182 6	70	29	-	-
7e	+14.102 1	53	03	43	-
2b ₂	+0.862 8	76	24	-	-
6e	-2.388 7	19	45	30	5
[OsNCl ₄] ⁻					
6a ₁	+9.226 9	59	10	29	-
4b ₁	+8.818 3	68	32	-	-
6e	+8.108 9	54	-	40	-
2b ₂	-4.643 6	73	26	-	-
5e	-7.924 3	14	57	27	-
[OsNBr ₄] ⁻					
6a ₁	+10.012 0	60	8	29	-
7e	+9.124 4	52	-	43	-
4b ₁	+9.051 0	65	34	-	-
2b ₂	-3.987 8	72	27	-	-
6e	-6.572 7	12	66	20	-

TABLE 3—MOLECULAR ORBITAL ENERGY FOR [OsNX₄(H₂O)]⁻ (X = Cl, Br)

Level	Energy eV	% Contribution			
		Os	<i>cis</i> -Cl	H ₂ O	N
[OsNCl ₄ (H ₂ O)] ⁻					
12a ₁	+9.146 8	68	30	-	-
7b ₁	+7.659 1	53	-	-	42
7b ₂	+7.649 5	54	-	-	41
11a ₁	+5.940 1	8	10	73	6
3a ₂	-4.215 6	73	26	-	-
6b ₁	-6.823 1	20	42	-	35
6b ₂	-6.830 1	20	42	-	36
10a ₁	-9.236 3	11	10	1	73
[OsNBr ₄ (H ₂ O)] ⁻					
12a ₁	+9.287 9	66	33	-	-
7b ₂	+8.885 0	52	-	-	44
9b ₁	+8.872 8	50	-	-	44
11a ₁	+6.949 3	8	10	72	6
3a ₂	-3.672 9	73	26	-	-
6b ₂	-5.970 3	16	56	-	25
8b ₁	-5.974 8	17	35	-	25
9a ₁	-9.265 1	9	10	-	76

Wiberg indices :

Bond strength results (as measured by Wiberg indices) are summarised in Table 4.

trans Effect in Os≡N complexes : For [OsNCl₄L]ⁿ⁻ (L = Cl, H₂O) and [OsNCl₄]⁻ (the case with no *trans*-ligand) ions, the values of the Os-N Wiberg indices show the trend [OsNCl₅]²⁻ < [OsNCl₄(H₂O)]⁻ < [OsNCl₄]⁻. For [OsNCl₄L]ⁿ⁻ (L = Cl or H₂O) ions, the distribution of electron density on the L-Os-N depends on the nature of the *trans*-L ligand and which in turn will cause a change in the strength of the

Os–N bond. The magnitude of the *trans*-influence of the L ligand can be judged from change in the strength of the Os–N bond. The decrease of Os–N fractional π -bond indices for $[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ [$W_\pi(\text{Os–N}) = 1.8914$] as compared to $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$ ($W_\pi(\text{Os–N}) = 1.9220$) and the increase of Os–N fraction σ -bond indices for $[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ [$W_\sigma(\text{Os–N}) = 1.209$] as compared to $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$ [$W_\sigma(\text{Os–N}) = 1.0668$] are observed. For $[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$, further increase of Os–N fractional σ -bond indices ($W_\sigma(\text{Os–N}) = 1.2941$) is observed. One can infer from these observations that greater π -donor properties of the *trans*-ligand (Cl is a better σ -donor than H_2O) increase the magnitude of the π -dative component of the Os–N bond and greater σ -donor properties of the *trans*-ligand (Cl is a better s -donor than H_2O) reduce the transfer of electron density from N–Os by σ -bonding. The values of the $W_\pi(\text{Os–N})$ which are comparable for $[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ and $[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$, suggest that the group H_2O appears to be pure σ -donor.

TABLE 4—BOND STRENGTHS (WIBERG INDICES) IN OSMIUM NITRIDO COMPLEXES

	$[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$	$[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$	$[\text{OsNBr}_4]^-$	$[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$	$[\text{OsNBr}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$
Os–N	2.988 9	3.184 4	3.117 2	3.100 4	3.050 1
σ	1.066 8	1.294 1	1.201 2	1.209 0	0.906 1
π	1.922 0	1.890 3	1.916 0	1.891 4	2.144 0
Os(<i>s</i>)–N	0.140 7	0.105 7	0.086 7	0.138 1	0.109 3
Os(<i>p</i>)–N	0.420 7	0.535 5	0.432 8	0.419 7	0.351 1
Os(<i>d</i>)–N	2.427 5	2.543 2	2.597 7	2.542 6	2.589 7
<i>cis</i> -Os–X	0.976 9	1.134 2	1.168 8	1.023 5	1.061 0
σ	0.834 9	0.908 0	0.917 7	0.853 0	0.870 9
π	0.142 0	0.226 2	0.251 1	0.170 5	0.190 1
Os(<i>s</i>)–X	0.174 9	0.218 4	0.224 5	0.182 0	0.194 9
Os(<i>p</i>)–X	0.509 7	0.600 0	0.630 3	0.535 7	0.564 3
Os(<i>d</i>)–X	0.292 3	0.316 1	0.314 0	0.305 8	0.301 8
<i>trans</i> -Os–L	0.780 3	–	–	0.215 7	0.196 6
σ	0.674 0	–	–	0.195 6	0.178 4
π	0.106 3	–	–	0.020 1	0.018 2
Os(<i>s</i>)–L	0.142 9	–	–	0.042 2	0.033 5
Os(<i>p</i>)–L	0.486 2	–	–	0.140 3	0.122 8
Os(<i>d</i>)–L	0.151 2	–	–	0.033 2	0.040 3

cis-Effect in $\text{Os}\equiv\text{N}$ complexes : For $[\text{OsNX}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ (X = Cl, Br) ligands located in the *cis*-position to the H_2O –Os–N coordinate (i.e. in the equatorial plane of the complex) introduce additional influence on the various interactions of nitrido complexes. Increase in the population of the σ -bonding orbitals of the *cis*-Os–X bond [Os–X σ -bond indices 0.8530 for X = Cl and 0.8709 for X = Br], on the substitution of bromide for chloride atom leads to decrease in the population of Os–OH₂ [Os–O σ -bond indices 0.1956 for *cis*-Cl and 0.1784 for *cis*-Br] and Os–N [Os–N σ -bond indices 1.2090 for *cis*-Cl and 0.9061 for *cis*-Br] bonds and hence decreasing the bond strength of Os–N and Os–O bonds. Though the Os–N π -bond indices are greater for $[\text{OsNBr}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ but the difference is not as great as between Os–N σ -bond indices. The similar trends are ob-

served in $[\text{OsNX}_4]^-$ (X = Cl or Br) complex ions.

Comparison of cis- and trans-ligand interactions : For $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$ complex ion, the Os(*s*)–Cl [*cis*-Os(*s*)–Cl = 0.1749, *trans*-Os(*s*)–Cl = 0.1429], Os(*p*)–Cl [*cis*-Os(*p*)–Cl = 0.5097, *trans*-Os(*p*)–Cl = 0.4862] and Os(*d*)–Cl [*cis*-Os(*d*)–Cl = 0.2922, *trans*-Os(*d*)–Cl = 0.1512] fractional bond indices are larger for the *cis*-bond and the largest difference between the components of the *cis*- and *trans*-Os–Cl bonds occurs with Os(*p*)–Cl components and hence favours the *cis*-bond.

It is possible to relate the amount of donation and back-donation to any experimental observable. The Os–N and *cis*-Os–Cl vibrational stretching frequencies^{1,3} are an attractive possibility for correlation. *cis*-Os–Cl stretching frequencies for $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$ (328), $[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ (335) and $[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$ (355 cm^{-1}) are proportional to square-root of *cis*-Os–Cl Wiberg indices. The Os–N stretching frequency for anionic osmium nitrido complexes is also linearly correlated with Os–N Wiberg indices.

TABLE 5—ORBITAL CHARGES AND GROSS ATOMIC CHARGE IN OSMIUM NITRIDO COMPLEXES

Complex ion	Orbital population		Atomic charge
	Os	N	
$[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$	6s 0.872 1	2s 1.421 8	Os, –0.667 8
	6p 2.602 8	2p 3.874 0	N, –0.295 8
	5d 5.192 9		<i>cis</i> -Cl, –0.179 0
	<i>cis</i> -Cl	<i>trans</i> -Cl	<i>trans</i> -Cl, –0.320 5
$[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$	3s 1.490 8	3s 1.556 4	
	3p 5.688 2	3p 5.764 1	
$[\text{OsNCl}_4]^-$	Os	N	
	6s 0.857 5	2s 1.392 8	Os, –0.659 8
	6p 2.567 2	2p 3.783 9	N, –0.176 7
	5d 5.235 1		<i>cis</i> -L, –0.040 8
$[\text{OsNBr}_4]^-$	<i>cis</i> -Cl		
	3s 1.440 9		
	3p 5.599 9		
$[\text{OsNBr}_4]^-$	Os	N	
	6s 0.879 2	2s 1.435 1	Os, –0.879 1
	6p 2.638 5	2p 3.743 5	N, –0.178 6
	5d 5.361 4		<i>cis</i> -Br, –0.014 3
$[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$	<i>cis</i> -Br		
	4s 1.466 9		
	4p 5.528 8		
$[\text{OsNCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$	Os	N	
	6s 0.866 2	2s 1.450 1	Os, –0.702 0
	6p 2.578 8	2p 3.739 1	N, –0.189 2
	5d 5.257 0		<i>cis</i> -Cl, –0.091 4
$[\text{OsNBr}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$	<i>cis</i> -Cl	O	
	3s 1.468 1	2s 1.386 1	
	3p 5.623 3	2p 4.742 1	
$[\text{OsNBr}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$	Os	N	
	6s 0.883 2	2s 1.483 3	Os, –0.893 4
	6p 2.639 1	2p 3.703 2	N, –0.186 5
	5d 5.371 1		<i>cis</i> -Br, –0.036 3
$[\text{OsNBr}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$	<i>cis</i> -Br	O	
	4s 1.480 2	2s 1.460 8	
	4p 5.556 1	2p 4.680 5	
			O, –0.141 3
			H, +0.183 3

Charge distribution :

Orbital charges and gross atomic charges are presented in Table 5. Mulliken population analysis assigns a positive charge on H₂O and negative charge on osmium nitrido chloro and bromo ligands. We will discuss the variation of atomic charges relative to [OsNCl₄]⁻ complex ion. For [OsNCl₄]⁻, (L = Cl, H₂O) upon substituting L in the *trans*-position, reduces the strength of the bonds already present, while the osmium, chlorine atoms and nitrido ligands become more negative. The trend in charge on nitrido ligand for [OsNCl₄L]ⁿ⁻, [OsNX₄]⁻ complex ions is the same as the trend of the Os-N Wiberg indices. The results of these calculations show that for [OsNCl₅]²⁻, the *trans*-Cl is a better electron-acceptor from the central metal atom than the *cis*-Cl.

Orbital populations :

The N(2p_π), N(2sp_σ) and Os(5d_π) orbital populations (Table 6) show trend. (i) There is a general decrease in the N(2p_π) populations in the series [OsNCl₄]⁻ > [OsNCl₄(H₂O)]⁻ > [OsNBr₄]⁻ > [OsNCl₅]²⁻ > [OsNBr₄(H₂O)]⁻. (ii) The N(2p_π) populations have minimum with [OsNBr₄(H₂O)]⁻. (iii) There is an increase in the Os(5d_π) populations in the series [OsNCl₄]⁻ < [OsNCl₄(H₂O)]⁻ < [OsNCl₅]²⁻ < [OsNBr₄]⁻ < [OsNBr₄(H₂O)]⁻. (iv) The Os(5d_π) populations have minimum with [OsNCl₄]⁻. (v) There is an increase in N(2sp_σ) orbital populations in the series [OsNCl₄]⁻ < [OsNCl₄(H₂O)]⁻ < [OsNBr₄]⁻ < [OsNBr₄(H₂O)]⁻ < [OsNCl₅]²⁻. These results suggest that the nitrido ligand is a better σ-donor and better π-donor in [OsNCl₄]⁻ complex ion.

TABLE 6—ORBITAL POPULATION FOR COMPLEX IONS

Complex ion	N (2sp _σ)	N (2p _π)	Os (5d _π)
[OsNCl ₅] ²⁻	3.116 6	2 179 7	1.875 0
[OsNCl ₄ (H ₂ O)] ⁻	2.948 8	2.240 4	1.832 7
[OsNBr ₄ (H ₂ O)] ⁻	3.039 1	2 147 4	1.918 6
[OsNCl ₄] ⁻	2.903 7	2.273 0	1.796 0
[OsNBr ₄] ⁻	2.987 2	2.191 4	1.877 4

Reactivity of osmium nitrido complexes : The reactions of transition metal nitrido complexes can be divided into two main groups : (a) reaction at the metal center; addition and substitution reactions and (b) reaction at the nitrido ligand.

Reaction type (a) : The hydrolytic behaviour of [OsNX₅]²⁻ (X = Cl, Br)¹⁶ indicates that the product is *trans*-[OsNX₄(H₂O)]⁻,

Griffith *et al.*⁷ reported convenient synthesis and various reactions of osmium nitrido complexes,

where, L = AsPh₃, SbPh₃, p_y, isoquinoline, pyridine-N-oxide, DMSO, 1/2 bipy etc.

Belmonto and Own⁹ showed that [OsNCl₄]⁻ can be alkylated to [OsNR_nCl_{4-n}]⁻ with MgR₂, XMgR or AlR₃ (n = 2 or R = CH₂CMe₃ or CH₂CH₂Ph; n = 4, R = Me).

Reaction type (b) : With triarylphosphine, [OsNX₄]⁻ (X = Cl, Br) and [OsNX₃(AsPh₃)₂] gave phosphineimido complexes [Os(NPR₃)X₃(PR₃)₂] by nucleophilic attack of PR₃ on the ligand⁷,

Osmium thionitrosyl complexes were prepared⁸ by the reaction of osmium nitrido complexes with S₂Cl₂,

where L = AsPh₃, PMe₂Ph, 1/2 bipy.

From the theoretical viewpoint, the electrophilic reactivity of a given substrate resides fundamentally in the (i) charge, (ii) energy of l.u.m.o. and (iii) localisation of l.u.m.o. By considering the net charge on the nitrido ligand (Table 5), one could infer that only [OsNCl₃(PH₃)₂] (charge on the nitrido ligand = 0.0150) is likely to be good reactant with nucleophiles and that the [OsNCl₅]²⁻, [OsNX₄(H₂O)]⁻ and [OsNX₄]⁻ (X = Cl, Br) complexes look like bad reactants.

The energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital is important in determining the product of the reaction. The calculated energy of l.u.m.o. decreases in the order [OsNCl₅]²⁻ > [OsNBr₄]⁻ > [OsNCl₄]⁻ > [OsNBr₄(H₂O)]⁻ > [OsNCl₄(H₂O)]⁻ > [OsNCl₃(PH₃)₂]. The energy of the l.u.m.o. for anionic osmium nitrido complexes is greater than that for [OsNCl₃(PH₃)₂] (energy of l.u.m.o. = -0.0914). An increase in the energy of l.u.m.o. for anionic osmium nitrido complexes increases the activation energy for electrophilic behaviour which favours substitution reaction or addition reaction over nucleophilic attack at the nitrido ligand of the Os-N group. The lower energy of l.u.m.o. for [OsNCl₃(PH₃)₂] favours the nucleophilic reaction at the nitrido ligand.

The orbital contributions to the l.u.m.o. are also important in determining the product of reaction. Table 2 shows that the metal contribution to the l.u.m.o. is higher for [OsNCl₅]²⁻, [OsNX₄]⁻ and lower for [OsNCl₃(PH₃)₂] (6% Os). The higher metal contributions to the l.u.m.o. for [OsNCl₅]²⁻ and [OsNX₄]⁻ suggest that electrophilic attack would take place at the osmium atom in these complexes. These conclusions are experimentally supported as aforementioned. One can also conclude from these observations that the reaction of triarylphosphine with [OsNX₄]⁻ results in the formation of [OsNCl₃(PR₃)₂] which reacts with PR₃ to give [Os(NPR₃)Cl₃(PR₃)₂].

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